

Cyano complexes of oxotungsten(IV) with aroyl hydrazone ligands

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Abstract : Reactions of $K_3Na[WO_2(CN)_4].6H_2O$ with aroyl hydrazone ligands namely benzoic acid[1-(furan-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BFMH), benzoic acid[(thiophene-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BTMH), benzoic acid[1-(thiophene-2-yl)ethylidene]hydrazide (BTEII), benzoic acid(phenylmethylene)hydrazide (BPMH) and benzoic acid[1-(anisol-3-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BAMH) in presence of acetic acid yield complexes of the type $[WO(CN)_3L-L]^-$. The complexes have been characterized by conductivity, magnetic susceptibility, IR, 1H NMR, UV-Vis and TGA/DTA studies. The ligands substitute one water and one cyanide group of the protonated $K_3Na[WO_2(CN)_4].6H_2O$ and bind in bidentate chelating mode. The mode of bonding of the ligands is confirmed by shifts observed in the 1H NMR spectrum of the ligand after complexation.

Keywords : Aroyl hydrazones, cyano complexes, triphenyl phosphine iminium chloride, 1H NMR, TGA/DTA.

Introduction

A series of oxo-cyano complexes of molybdenum(IV) and tungsten(IV) with various monodentate ligands of formula $[M(CN)_4O(L)]^{n-}$, where $L = NCS^-$, N_3^- , F^- , HCN and py (pyridine); $M = Mo$ or W have been synthesised and characterised¹⁻³. The protonation of the dioxotetracyano complexes of molybdenum(IV), tungsten(IV), rhenium(V), technetium(V) results in the formation of $[MO(OH)(CN)_4]^{(n+1)-}$ and $[MO(H_2O)(CN)_4]^{n-}$ complexes and have been studied in detail over the past decade^{4,5}. These protonated species undergo aqua substitution reactions by monodentate ligands^{6,7} and both aqua and cyano substitution by bidentate ligands^{8,9}. The protonation behaviour of these systems has been the subject of C-13 and O-17 NMR studies in order to investigate the water exchange of these complex ions¹⁰.

The existence of protonated forms was duly established by means of the structure determination of $[Cr(en)_3][MoO(OH)(CN)_4].H_2O$, $[Pt(en)_2][MoO(H_2O)(CN)_4].2H_2O$ and $(PPh_4)_2[MoO(H_2O)(CN)_4].4H_2O$ ^{11,12}. These structure determinations as well as the structural data of $[MoO_2(CN)_4]^{4-}$ showed that $Mo=O$ and $Mo-OH$ bonds are much stronger than the $Mo-OH_2$ bonds¹³. It was found that the bidentate ligand 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) reacts with *trans*- $[MoO_2(CN)_4]^{4-}$ resulting in the formation

of $[MoO(phen)(CN)_3]^-$ ^{14,15}. This ground-state stabilization of the metal-oxygen bond on protonation indicates that it is actually protonated forms that are reactive towards substitution. This supposition was confirmed by the observation that no reaction occurred at a high pH where $[MoO_2(CN)_4]^{4-}$ is the main species. The fact that a cyano ligand was also displaced from the parent ion raised the question of which ligand (aqua, hydroxo or cyano) will first be substituted during a presumably two-step substitution process with a bidentate ligand. The crystal structure determination of $Cs_2Na[MoO(N_3)(CN)_4]$ ¹⁶ clearly indicated that aqua ligand is preferentially substituted by the azide ligand.

Complexes of the type $[MO(L-L)(CN)_3]^{(n+1)-}$, where $L-L = 2,2'$ -bipyridyl (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen), pyridine-2-carboxylate (pic) and several Schiff bases and $M = Mo$ or W have been studied in detail¹⁷⁻²². The cyano complexes of Mo^{IV} and W^{IV} with organic ligands have found application in the study of solvation effects¹⁷.

Hydrazones are an important class of organic compounds²³⁻²⁶, some of which show significant biological activities. Moreover, in many cases, it has been suggested that some biological activities of organic compounds increased by the coordination with metals²⁷. For example, ligand 3,4,5-triphenolbenzoyl salicylaldehyde hydrazone

and its Rare Earth metal complexes have been prepared and their antitumor activities were compared and it has been found that the complexes were more effective than ligand²⁸.

A considerable number of relatively fast reactions of $[\text{MO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ with different ligands and importance of hydrazone ligands as biological active species prompted us to use a similar procedure to obtain tricyano complexes of tungsten(IV) with aroylhydrazones ligands which form a variety of complexes with different transition metals^{29,30}. The structures of ligands are given below :

BFMH, where X = O and R = H

BTMH, where X = S and R = H

BTEH, where X = S and R = CH₃

BPMH, where R¹ = H

BAMH, where R¹ = OCH₃BTEH

Results and discussion

The reaction of $[\text{WO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ with benzoic acid[1-(furan-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BFMH), benzoic acid[(thiophene-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BTMH), benzoic acid[1-(thiophene-2-yl)ethylidene]hydrazide (BTEH), benzoic acid(phenylmethylene)hydrazide (BPMH) and benzoic acid[1-(anisole-3-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BAMH) takes place according to the equation,

leading to the formation of complex $[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}]^-$, where L-L = BFMH, BTMH, BTEH, BPMH and BAMH.

Since the equilibrium lies strongly towards the reactants, formation of product complex can be observed only in concentrated solutions in the presence of large excess of ligand. The complexes were isolated as bis(triphenylphosphine) iminium salts and as cesium salts. The $(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{NH}_2^+$ or Cs^+ cations form insoluble salts only with the product complex, thus shifting the equilibrium to the right. The analytical and spectroscopic results (Table 1) showed that all the complexes are mononuclear with general formula, $\text{Cs}[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1-5) and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{NH}_2^+[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (6, 7), where L-L = BFMH, BTMH, BTEH, BPMH and BAMH. All the complexes are colored, stable, insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents like DMF and DMSO. The complexes have characteristic melting points.

Conductance measurements :

The molar conductivity (measured in 10^{-3} M DMF solution) of these complexes is in the range of 82–103 mho $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1) which indicates the uni-univalent electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements at 30 °C indicates the diamagnetic nature of the complexes.

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of all the complexes exhibit a sharp band in the region of 933–952 cm^{-1} due to the $\nu(\text{W}=\text{O})$ stretching mode²⁰. In the CN stretching region the IR spectra show two bands in the region of 2066 to 2191 cm^{-1} .

The IR spectra for free ligands are consistent with existence of aroyl hydrazones. A strong and sharp band at ca. 3250 cm^{-1} in all ligands is due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ stretching mode. Two strong bands at 1660–1650 cm^{-1} and 1640–1625 cm^{-1} are attributed to amide $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ modes respectively, indicating that ligands exist in keto form³¹. All complexes exhibit a strong absorption band at ca. 3200–3269 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ stretching mode suggesting that all the ligands remain protonated on chelation. The amide bands $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ are shifted to lower frequencies in the spectra of complexes suggesting the involvement of carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen in coordination with metal³². Thus, these ob-

Table 1. Analytical data and some physical properties of oxotungsten(IV) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Mol. wt. (g/mol)	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					λ_M (mho cm ² mol ⁻¹)
					C	H	N	S	W	
1.	Cs[WO(CN) ₃ BFMH].H ₂ O	643.04	Greenish white	222	28.42 (28.01)	2.10 (1.86)	10.71 (10.88)	-	27.93 (28.58)	100
2.	Cs[WO(CN) ₃ BTMH].H ₂ O	659.10	Greenish white	235	27.12 (27.33)	2.02 (1.82)	10.12 (10.62)	5.10 (4.86)	27.10 (27.89)	103
3.	Cs[WO(CN) ₃ BTEH].H ₂ O	673.13	Greenish yellow	240	28.00 (28.54)	1.93 (2.07)	10.10 (10.39)	4.93 (4.76)	26.43 (27.31)	100
4.	Cs[WO(CN) ₃ BPMH].H ₂ O	653.07	Greenish white	244	30.98 (31.26)	2.43 (2.14)	11.11 (10.71)	-	27.18 (28.15)	82
5.	Cs[WO(CN) ₃ BAMH].H ₂ O	683.10	Greenish white	248	31.72 (31.64)	2.30 (2.34)	10.94 (10.24)	-	26.12 (26.91)	90
6.	(Ph ₃ P) ₂ NH ₂ [WO(CN) ₃ BFMH].3H ₂ O	1086.38	Greenish yellow	225	36.01 (36.48)	2.88 (2.45)	7.54 (7.73)	-	16.70 (16.92)	96
7.	(Ph ₃ P) ₂ NH ₂ [WO(CN) ₃ BFMH].BTMH].3H ₂ O	1102.44	Greenish yellow	246	35.69 (35.95)	2.80 (2.44)	7.90 (7.61)	3.00 (2.90)	16.34 (16.67)	99

servations suggest that the ligands behave as neutral bidentate chelating type coordinating metal through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit intense peaks in the region 371–411 nm. A peak of low intensity is also observed in the region 559–602 nm. The bands observed in the region 371–411 nm can be assigned to ligand to metal charge-transfer (LMCT) transition. The weak bands observed in the region 559–602 nm can be attributed to *d-d* transitions.

¹H NMR :

The ¹H NMR spectra of ligands in DMSO show low field signals at 11.8–11.4 ppm for the imino proton confirming the existence of ligands in keto form. The CH=N peak is observed at 8.40–8.60 ppm and signal due to aromatic protons which occur as multiplets appear between δ 6.4–7.8 ppm. The spectra of BTEH ligand shows resonance at 2.43 ppm due to CH₃ protons. The spectra of all complexes show low field signals for imino proton at nearly same δ value as that of corresponding free ligands. Moreover, CH=N peak in complexes is shifted towards higher δ value (8.72–9.00) due to deshielding because of bonding of azomethine nitrogen with tungsten.

TGA/DTA studies :

TG curve for the complex Cs[WO(CN)₃BTMH].H₂O shows weight loss of 2.8% upto 235 °C corresponding to

the loss of one water molecule (calcd. wt. loss = 2.6%). This is also indicated by an endothermic peak of 11.681 μ V in the DTA curve at 270 °C. Further heating results in gradual and continuous weight loss (33.49%) upto about 512 °C which corresponds to loss of ligand (BTMH) (calcd. wt. loss = 34.28%). This is also indicated by a sharp endothermic peak of 19.364 μ V in the DTA curve at 484 °C. After this no weight loss is observed up to 800 °C. This indicates a stable complex of the composition Cs[WO(CN)₃].

Based on the above observations, it is proposed that these complexes are hexa-coordinated with +4 oxidation state of metal and of general composition, [WO(CN)₃L-L]⁻ (where L-L = BFMH, BTMH, BTEH, BPMH and BAMH). The representative structure proposed for the complexes is as :

where, L-L = BFMH, BTMH, BTEH, BPMH and BAMH

Experimental

Reagent grade furfuraldehyde (Himedia), thiophen-2-carboxaldehyde (Himedia), 2-acetylthiophene (Himedia), benzaldehyde (Ranbaxy), anisaldehyde (Himedia), benzhydrazide (Fluka), sodium tungstate dihydrate and potassium cyanide (SDS) were used as received. Bis(triphenylphosphine)iminium chloride $[(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{-NH}_2]\text{Cl}$, cesium chloride and other laboratory reagent were of analytical grade (Sigma, Aldrich) and used as supplied. The solvent used for the synthesis of ligands and their complexes were distilled before use. The ligands were prepared by the reported method³⁰. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were analysed microanalytically using CHNS analyzer Leco make model-932. Tungsten was analysed by gravimetric method³³. Molar conductivity at room temperature in DMF (10^{-3} M) was measured using an Elicoconductivity Bridge, type CM82T and a conductivity cell with cell constant of 0.74. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was recorded at room temperature using Gouy's balance and using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a standard. IR spectra of complexes over the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr disc. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded using a double beam UV-spectrophotometer type SL-164. Thermogravimetric analysis (DTA-DTG-TG) of representative complex was recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Pyris Diamond) thermoanalyser at the heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in an atmosphere of air.

Preparation of complexes :

$\text{K}_3\text{Na}[\text{WO}_2(\text{CN})_4].6\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

10.0 g (0.03 mol) of sodium tungstate dihydrate, 3.0 g (0.063 mol) of sodium borohydride and 5.0 g (0.077 mol) of potassium cyanide were dissolved in 100 ml water followed by dropwise addition of 5 ml (0.08 mol) acetic acid over 10 min. An additional 5.0 g (0.077 mol) of potassium cyanide was added, followed by dropwise addition of another 5 ml (0.08 mol) acetic acid over 10 min. Solid sodium hydroxide (20 g, 0.05 mol) was added slowly to the tungsten(VI) solution followed by the slow addition of 30 ml ethanol. The brownish-yellow crystals were decanted and washed successively with five ca. 100 ml portions of an ethanol : water (9 : 1) mixture. Recrystallization was performed by dissolving the crystals in a minimum quantity of water, addition of ca. 1 g each of NaOH and KOH and precipitation of the K_3Na -

$[\text{WO}_2(\text{CN})_4].6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the slow addition of ethanol (yield ~ 60%, 10 g). The structure of $\text{K}_3\text{Na}[\text{WO}_2(\text{CN})_4].6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : Na, 4.31; K, 22.00; W, 34.01; O, 18.05; C, 8.50; N, 11.05; H, 2.33. Calcd. : Na, 4.28; K, 21.87; W, 34.28; O, 17.89; C, 8.9; N, 10.44; H, 2.20%) and the infrared spectrum (KBr) which exhibited band at 968 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{W}=\text{O})$ and at 2080 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$.

$\text{Cs}[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}].\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

$\text{Cs}[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}].\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Table 1) (L-L = benzoic acid[1-(furan-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BFMH), benzoic acid[(thiophene-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BTMH), benzoic acid[1-(thiophene-2-yl)ethylidene]hydrazide (BTEH), benzoic acid(phenylmethylene)hydrazide (BPMH) and benzoic acid[1-(anisol-3-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BAMH)) were prepared by dissolving 3.31 g (5.8 mmol) of $\text{K}_3\text{Na}[\text{WO}_2(\text{CN})_4].6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 15 ml of water and to this was added 24 mmol of ligands; BFMH (5.14 g), BTMH (5.52 g), BTEH (5.86 g), BPMH (5.38 g) and BAMH (6.10 g), in 20 ml of ethanol. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.0 with 0.5 M acetic acid. A 1.0 g sample of CsCl (6 mmol) was dissolved in 10 ml of water. Both the solutions were heated to about $35\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and mixed. The orange-red solution initially obtained on standing for about 24 h at room temperature leads to the formation of complexes. These were filtered off and washed by ethanol (yield 32–40%).

$(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{NH}_2[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

$(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{NH}_2[\text{WO}(\text{CN})_3\text{L-L}].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (L-L = benzoic acid[1-(furan-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BFMH) and benzoic acid[(thiophene-2-yl)methylene]hydrazide (BTMH)) were prepared by dissolving 3.31 g (5.8 mmol) of $\text{K}_3\text{Na}[\text{WO}_2(\text{CN})_4].6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 15 ml of water and to this was added 24 mmol of ligand; BFMH (5.14 g), BTMH (5.52 g) in 20 ml of ethanol. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7 with 0.5 M acetic acid. It was heated to about $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 min followed by addition of 3.44 g (6 mmol) of $(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}$ in 15 ml of water. An oily product which sticks to the beaker and the glass rod was obtained on stirring. The solution was decanted and the oily product was extracted with ethanol when complexes precipitated. The precipitate was filtered off, washed several times with water, and dried in vacuum (yield 40–48%).

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